

effective.

SR26BM was evaluated for yield in the regular Salt Tolerant Variety Trial (see table). The yield potential and puffing quality of the grain seemed unaffected. The plant type of SR26BM—tall and weak—needs improvement, but the variety can be cultivated in the dry season in salt-affected soils. ■

BW100, a promising new variety in Sri Lanka

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BW100, a sister line of BW78, was selected in 1976 from the cross H50I//Podiwee A-8/H5. Since 1976 it has consistently yielded higher than BW78. Its gall midge resistance was shown in 1977 and 1978 yala, when it outyielded several varieties, including BG11-11.

In the 1978 Yala National Coordinated Rice Varietal Trials tested at 14 locations, BW100 gave the highest mean yield—11.4 t/ha under various soil and climatic conditions. In the 1977-78 Maha Extension Field Trials, it outyielded BW78 in six of seven districts.

The intermediate-statured BW100 matures in 4–4.5 months; responds well to nitrogen; has lodging resistance, weed competitive ability, superior grain quality, and resistance to storage pests; and performs well under adverse soil and climatic conditions. ■

Sita: a variety for irrigated wetlands of Bihar, India

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In 1975, the variety Sita (from the cross IR12-178-2-3/IR8) was released in Bihar for the intensively cropped irrigated areas.

Sita's relatively short growth duration (130-135 days, seed to seed) enables farmers to harvest by early November, then plant a winter crop such as wheat.

Yields average 4 to 6 t/ha. Farmers prefer Sita to Jaya because it responds better to low levels of fertilizer (40–50 kg N/ha); it has long, slender grain; it is moderately resistant to tungro, blast, and bacterial blight; and its flowering is synchronous. Bihar farmers have adopted Sita widely and the variety is moving into Uttar Pradesh. ■

Optimal use of space and plant containers in RGA

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Rapid generation advance (RGA) makes it possible to have 3 generations/year of breeding materials by reducing the growth duration, shortening the day length, and using high temperature. Spacing must also be close to plant thousands of progeny lines in a greenhouse of limited size. Use of large wooden boxes or individual plots has advantages and disadvantages. More plants can be accommodated in wooden boxes, but those boxes remain occupied until the last plant is harvested. Small pots take more space – but half of that space may be available 3 months after sowing. If plants are stressed at an early stage, elimination of susceptible lines provides additional space within a month after sowing.

An experiment was conducted at IRRI to study plant responses and advantages of different containers. Pregerminated F₂ seeds of the cross IR24389 (Sein Ta Lay (X69-2-27)/IR36//BKN6986-147-2), designated as RGA 079 were planted in wooden boxes, square pots, and round pots. The measurements of the wooden boxes were 1.27 × 1.27 × 0.1 m; each accommodated 1,600 plants at a spacing of 3 × 3 cm. In an equivalent area, 440 square pots (5.5 × 5.5 × 5.0 cm) can be accommodated but only 272 round pots (6.7 cm diam, 5 cm ht). We used Maahas soil mixed with ammonium sulfate, solophos, and muriate of potash at the rate of 4-2-2 g/4 kg of soil. The plants were grown in the greenhouse under natural day length until the 5th-leaf stage; then they were subjected

to a short-day treatment of 10 hours light and 14 hours darkness. Additional nitrogen fertilizer was applied at the rate of 20 g ammonium sulfate/box at 15-day intervals.

The wooden box accommodated twice as many plants per unit of space as the pots did. The population reached 50% flowering at about the same time regardless of container. That means that half of a population planted in pots can be harvested after 90 days. The vacated space can be used to start another set of cross progeny. When wooden boxes are used, the space vacated is wasted and the box cannot be used to full efficiency until the last plant is harvested.

The number of plants processed per year is essentially the same regardless of whether wooden boxes or square pots are used. Wooden boxes may have an advantage for early generation materials that are not screened or selected and that require small amounts of seeds per plant.

The closer spacing of the large wooden box resulted in more dead plants at harvest. Closer spacing means more competition - not only for nutrients, even more so for light. In the wooden box, 74% of the plants survived; in the square pots 99% did; and in the round pots, 100%.

For screening, the individual plant containers are definitely better than the large wood boxes. Susceptible plants can be eliminated after testing; the remaining few plants can grow to maturity in a much smaller space.

The square pot is ideal for RGA screening, which is usually done at the F₄ or F₅ generation. In RGA, more seeds are needed for distribution to plant breeders because panicles are larger and scientists can easily discard dead or susceptible plants. ■

Rice breeding progress at Bombuwela, Sri Lanka

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The variety H4 was released in 1959 and, like IR8 in Southeast Asia, it initiated the so-called green revolution in Sri Lanka. It

was most popular in the dry and intermediate zones for more than a decade. But in the low country wet zone it performed poorly because of disease, insect, climatic, and soil problems. Similar problems have caused the improved varieties such as BG11-11 and BG90-2 to perform poorly in the low country wet zone.

Until recently, the general opinion was that the area had low potential for rice. But the problems, particularly iron toxicity in mineral soils, were overemphasized.

The situation became clearer with the initiation of land classification of the wet zone. After problem areas were isolated, we could determine priorities. We have dropped the concept of releasing one variety to cover the entire area. Our present breeding program is geared to

breed specific varieties to overcome problems peculiar to the following specific conditions: 1) tolerance for flash floods, 2) ability of seed to germinate under standing water, 3) rapid seedling growth, 4) ability to compete with weeds, 5) tolerance for adverse soils, 6) resistance to diseases and insects, 7) resistance to storage pests, 8) palatability, and 9) red pericarp.

Some of the local varieties screened and the traits peculiar to them follow:

- Muhudukiriyal — salinity tolerance
- Karamana, Molligoda, and Sula — ability to emerge through standing water
- Deverreddiri — tolerance for floods and iron toxicity
- Podiwee A-8 — resistance to storage pests
- Batapolayal — rapid seedling growth

The results of screening of early generation material for resistance to gall midge, thrips, and iron toxicity are encouraging. In 1978 we began to test our promising materials in farmers' fields of varying land classes.

From the 4 to 4.5-month age group, LD66 and BW78 have been released and successfully cultivated in the wet zone. BW100 awaits release. Although we have released varieties for successful cultivation in the mineral and half bog soil, we have yet to find an alternative to the local variety Deverreddiri, which is grown on about 10% of the rice area on the coastal floodplains.

In all modesty, we can state that we have contributed positively toward the goal of making our country self-sufficient in rice. ■

Importance of flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio in rice improvement

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The importance in rice yield improvement of physiological traits such as flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio was studied through statistical tools.

One hundred twenty rices were selected from the germplasm maintained at Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India. The strains were classified into four groups based on maturity period and plant height: early

short, late short, early tall, and late tall. Thirty varieties in each group were grown in a randomized block design with three replications. The usual cultural practices were followed. Data on flag leaf area, and grain-straw ratio were collected from 10 randomly selected plants/replication.

Flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio varied widely in all groups. Although the range can provide an estimate of variability in the germplasm, the coefficient of variability could be more reliable. The grain-straw ratio showed a high coefficient of genetic and phenotypic variability (see table). The flag leaf area also showed appreciable coefficient

of variation.

Heritability (which provides a basis for making selections based on the phenotypic performance) and expected genetic advance were high for both traits in all groups.

The study showed a strong positive correlation between yield and grain-straw ratio in the early short (0.5202) and the late tall group (0.6632) and only a positive correlation in the early tall (0.2305) and late short (0.3431) groups. The flag leaf area and yield were correlated positively and significantly in the early short group (0.4075) but only positively in the other groups (see table). ■

Statistical parameters for flag leaf area and grain-straw ratio in various rice cultures, Ludhiana, India, 1979.^a

	Early short		Late short		Early tall		Late tall	
	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grainstraw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio	Flag leaf area (cm)	Grain-straw ratio
Mean ± SE	40.544 ± 3.219	0.872 ± 0.065	31.185 ± 2.142	0.802 ± 0.033	56.991 ± 4.118	0.466 ± 0.028	58.574 ± 3.144	0.441 ± 0.027
Range	24.14 – 59.61	0.33 – 1.30	25.54 – 62.47	0.31 – 1.20	25.99 – 83.21	0.31 – 0.61	31.33 – 90.50	0.15 – 0.75
Coefficient of phenotypic variation (%)	25.51	28.08	23.25	30.02	27.82	27.18	23.94	31.30
Heritability (%)	21.49	24.83	19.56	29.13	24.84	24.99	21.63	29.35
Expected genetic advance (as % of mean)	40.73	45.30	36.66	58.26	44.47	47.10	43.65	56.71
Phenotypic correlation with yield	0.4075*	0.5202**	0.1653	0.3431	0.4200*	0.2305	0.1868	0.6632**
Genotypic correlation with yield	0.4966	0.5233	0.1947	0.3919	0.5585	0.2846	0.2210	0.7635

^a*Significant at 5% level. **Significant at 1% level.